

Navigating new frontiers: Developing an evaluation model for a local and civic-led outreach project in Mexico, the case of Tribu Cultura Astronómica's Astronomy Festival

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This article focuses on developing feasible evaluation models for civic-led astronomy for development programmes in the Global South and, more specifically, astro-tourism initiatives. Using the case of the 3rd Astronomy Festival, implemented in Mexico by Tribu Cultura Astronómica (Tribu) in 2023 and 2024. We will describe the methodological approach, methods and techniques used to develop an evaluation model that was feasible and adapted to local needs using the Theory of Change (ToC).

Introduction

Astronomy for Development (AFD) is a new and growing field that aims to increase the impact of astronomy education and outreach. AFD became a part of the strategic vision of the International Astronomical Union (IAU) in 2009 to advance the use of astronomy to promote human and societal development. One of the applications of AFD is astro-tourism, defined as "activities focused on observing night skies and celestial phenomena in natural spaces, which contributes to communities' involvement, empowerment and participation and to regional development." (*Tapada et al., 2021, p. 291*).

Due to its emergent nature, the true impact of AFD is currently more of a promise than an evidence-based reality. In addition, field-specific methodologies of AFD programmes are scarce (*Chapman et al., 2015; Pompea & Russo, 2020*), especially those adapted and applied to scenarios of small-scale, grassroots, civic-led initiatives and further localised in developing countries in the Global South (*Russo, 2015*).

We will describe the development process and design of an evaluation model applicable to the 3rd Astronomy Festival implemented by Tribu Cultura Astronómica, a civil society organisation (CSO) whose mission is to improve scientific culture in Mexico through astronomy outreach and education. In particular, we will share the methodological approaches, methods, and techniques used to develop a Theory of

Change (ToC) as a tool to map and assess the expectations and assumptions of how Tribu's programme has a potentially positive impact on local, sustainable development. It is worth noting that the evaluation model resulted from the pro bono work of ProSociedad as Tribu's partner organisation.

Tribu was founded in 2021 during COVID-19's confinement policy to promote positive recreational activities, such as stargazing, that can be done from home, rooftops, backyards or streets in open spaces. Tribu now serves local communities in Mexico with a range of programmes related to astronomy education, especially by training teachers in basic education to promote STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics) interest. Additionally, through its outreach programme, Tribu engages new audiences mainly through large-scale public stargazing parties. Finally, through the astro-tourism programme, Tribu promotes economic opportunities, especially for young women who want to engage in tourism services, in alliance with local governments and businesses, such as hotels and restaurants. In all these initiatives, Tribu does its own way through innovative approaches, such as theatre, clowns, circuses, and general entertainment and amusement, to fulfil the promise of reaching those astronomy has not yet reached.

Since its origin, Tribu has been focusing on building and sharing evidence on astronomy for development initiatives. For this reason, since its inception, Tribu has

implemented an evaluation and learning agenda throughout its different phases (Figure 1). In 2021, ProSociedad, a sustainable development agency specialising in capacity building, accompanied Tribu in developing a strategic planning process that included recognising the needs of science and astronomy education in Mexico and establishing a tactical plan to contribute to this issue. In 2022, during the implementation of the 2nd Astronomy Festival, Tribu collected the first user survey to try to understand users' profiles and what they valued the most about their programmes. Later, in 2023, in the context of implementing the 3rd Astronomy Festival, the organisation decided they were ready to develop a more in-depth evaluation model, using a ToC that could map potential contributions of their work in astro-tourism. This article will describe how this process happened.

In the following sections, we will first provide a context on evaluation methodology in general and specifically for AFD programmes. Later, we will describe the scope and limitations of these methodologies when applied to AFD, astronomy education and outreach programmes. We will then present how this was put into practice in the case of the 3rd Astronomy Festival led by Tribu, highlighting the adaptations made and their limitations. Finally, we will share some reflections on the lessons learned and future opportunities to advance the research agenda of AFD initiatives worldwide.

Figure 1: Tribu's journey through evaluation and learning.

Background

The effectiveness of AFD programmes relies on the generation of evidence and a knowledge base to deliver on their promise of impact on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and to attract the attention and funding they need. However, there is still a lack of empirical evidence on the effects of astronomy education and outreach programmes on sustainable development (Chapman et al., 2015; Bretones, 2019).

The lack of hard evidence on the impact of AFD limits its use and expansion worldwide (Russo, 2015), especially in developing countries where competing resources for other basic needs make this investment, without an evidence base, a luxury. This is coupled with concerns about the ethical use of resources invested in AFD programmes and particularly the prevention of negative unintended consequences of these initiatives on vulnerable populations, such as disruptions to indigenous or local cultural practices or environmental impact on local ecosystems due to increased tourism activity (Grant, 2015).

Developing the theory of change: methodology, process and adaptations

As a case study, in general, the Astronomy Festival of Tribu consists of various outreach activities (Figure 2), and in its 3rd edition, it focused its attention on the use of astrotourism as a mechanism to attract new audiences to outreach activities within semi-rural and rural areas. The festival included implementing a "Star Party" in each of the

three participating tourist-oriented locations, locally known as Magic Towns, in the state of Jalisco. This programme was also supported by a strategic alliance with the Ministry of Tourism of Jalisco, which opened the door to local tourism offices in the municipal government.

Methodological approaches and methods

The methodological approaches and methods used to develop the 3rd Astronomy Festival evaluation model were drawn from two areas of knowledge and practice: impact evaluation of development interventions and AFD evaluation frameworks.

From the first area of knowledge, we used the ToC to evaluate the 3rd Astronomy Festival. This methodology helps a programme or project designer identify assumptions and expectations about how and why the intervention should work, describing the causal relationships between the activities and the expected impact (Rossi et al., 2004; Stein & Valters, 2012). We also adopted a participatory action research (PAR) approach, which consists of the active involvement of community members or stakeholders in every stage of the research process, from identifying issues to developing solutions, emphasising collaboration, reflection, and action to create lasting change (Kindon et al., 2007). We did this by gathering the perceptions of the project's internal and external stakeholders through in-depth interviews and observation to collectively define the plausible ToC and focus on the learning process associated with constructing the ToC itself. Finally, we

Figure 2: Activities involved in the 3rd Astronomy Festival. Image Credit: Tribu Cultura Astronómica

Figure 3: Organisational theory of change of Tribu Cultura Astronómica. Image Credit: Adapted from Tribu Cultura Astronómica (2021)

decided to approach the evaluation framework from a decision-oriented impact evaluation approach (Shah *et al.*, 2015) rather than an academic impact evaluation approach. This means we prioritised collecting and analysing information by considering the stakeholder's demands and the questions and decisions they wanted the evaluation to address.

Specifically, from the area of AFD evaluation frameworks, we used the Chapman *et al.* (2015) approach to develop a ToC for the outreach programme of the IAU Office of Astronomy for Development (OAD). In the paper, the outreach programme ToC was informed and linked to an organisational strategic plan or "high-level" ToC. Following this idea, in the case of Tribu, we used their organisational strategic plan or "high level" ToC (Figure 3), developed in 2021 as a starting point to develop the 3rd Astronomy Festival ToC.

Tribu's strategic plan, or "high-level" ToC, was built in 2021 in collaboration with ProSociedad. It was initially built from a qualitative analysis of the needs around scientific culture in Mexico and defined the organisation's purpose or mission. This model was built from public data on scientific culture among children and youth in Mexico. It also included a literature review of the best available evidence on astronomy outreach and education programmes and a validation phase from

local, national, and international science and astronomy communication experts.

Processes and techniques to develop the evaluation methodology

Following a backward design approach (Wiggins & McTighe, 2005) that proposes that the best way to design an intervention is to derive or deduct its elements from the expected results (and not the other way around), we decided to build the evaluation framework for the 3rd Astronomy Festival by first establishing the purpose of the festival and, from there, mapping how the components and activities of the project fit into the expected goals.

To define the purpose, we conducted a literature review of existing evaluation frameworks relevant to the Astronomy Festival's potential impact to map potential changes within the festival's design. We considered existing evaluation frameworks, some of them produced by the IAU and the OAD (Frechtling, 2002; Allen *et al.*, 2008; Lelliott & Rollnick, 2010; Chapman *et al.*, 2015; Grant, 2015; Bartlett, 2024). We also considered relevant astro-tourism evaluation cases worldwide (Masters *et al.*, 2018; Van Wyk-Jacobs, 2018; Mitchell & Gallaway, 2019; Jacobs *et al.*, 2020; Rodrigues *et al.*, 2022; Tarek *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, we searched for other relevant studies of astronomy education and outreach in Mexico (Bravo-Alfaro *et al.*, 2019).

To determine how the components and activities of the 3rd Astronomy Festival fit or contributed to the purpose, we approached the main stakeholders of the Festival through semi-structured interviews. We contacted four main stakeholders: two internal and one external to Tribu. Internally, we interviewed Tribu's leaders and founders and their staff. Through in-depth interviews, we also consulted the main allies of the 2023-2024 edition of the Astronomy Festival, namely the tourism directors of the three participating municipalities and the primary contact at the State Ministry of Tourism. We additionally included audience perspectives through observation and informal conversations during the 3rd Astronomy Festival.

Following the data collection, all the elements were integrated into a logic model in the form of a ToC, which represents the causal chain of how, starting from the definition of a problem statement, the intervention of the Astronomy Festival and its components will hypothetically generate outputs, outcomes and final results (impact), and how all this together will eventually lead to the achievement of the initially defined purpose.

Results and limitations

Figure 4 shows the final ToC for Tribu's Astronomy Festival. The diagram below outlines a pathway to improve science culture and local economic development in small tourist communities in Jalisco using astro-tourism. Guided by the principles of equal access, inclusiveness, and adaptability, the festival organises "star parties" with telescope observations, astronomy lectures, and interactive experiences. These activities aim to raise scientific awareness among children and stimulate interest in astro-tourism among local stakeholders. Expected outcomes include increased access to science education, improved youth science literacy, and increased local economic revenue from tourism. The success of the model depends on the favourable political and economic conditions, effective resource allocation, and strong local commitment.

The arrows illustrate the relationships between these elements: solid arrows represent direct cause-and-effect relationships, while dotted arrows indicate

Figure 4: Theory of Change of the 3rd Astronomy Festival.

indirect or secondary pathways of influence. Dotted double-sided arrows indicate two-way relationships or feedback loops. Taken together, these components illustrate how the Festival's activities are expected to lead to enhanced science culture and local economic development through astro-tourism.

In the Festival ToC (Figure 4), the numbers 1 through 7 serve as reference points to guide the reader through the sequential logic of the model, highlighting key elements of its design that also contrast with the previous organisational ToC (Figure 3). These elements are described below:

- The ToC begins with the Principles of Action. This element was introduced to clarify the key features of how the Festival is implemented to deliver an impact. In the interviews, local allies emphasised the way that Tribu built a relationship with them and how the Tribu team related to the audience was impactful. Three principles of action were identified as critical:
 - Creating an “equalising” environment, in the sense that almost everyone, regardless of age or gender, was in the same position in terms of knowledge and could experience the same awe looking through telescopes and participating in the short talks. This is particularly relevant in polarisation due to generational, ideological and gen-

der inequalities. This aspect was highlighted by an ally in Tapalpa, who mentioned that locals and tourists were equally involved in the activity, which rarely happens.

- Another principle highlighted by local allies as critical to the development of the star parties was the emphasis on leaving no one behind, and the focus on reaching new audiences, engaging each and every person who participated, and making every effort to be inclusive. This principle is manifested by the fact that Tribu designs the experience to make the greatest effort to reach audiences who have never had access by making it open and free, while removing economic barriers to access. Another aspect of inclusivity was the Tribu team's ability to adapt the language to reach everyone, connecting with 6-year lads and adults simultaneously, engaging them with questions, conversation, and even jokes.
 - Adaptability to local conditions (space, resources, etc.) was also seen as critical by local allies. All the allies established that they had never had an outreach experience before, not only at night but also in science communication activities open to the public.
- Tribu's organisational ToC (Figure 3) defines the focus in trying to address youth science culture in Mexico. The

problem definition has been adapted to reflect that the core issue of this specific programme is to intervene in small rural tourist towns in the state of Jalisco, while maintaining the focus on young people.

- In contrast to the organisational ToC (Figure 3), the Festival ToC (Figure 4) contains a description of inputs and activities. These elements highlight the most tangible aspects of the Festival, which consist of a combination of educational, entertainment, and astronomy outreach activities; telescope viewing, short astronomy talks, and what Tribu calls “sensory stimuli”, which include large inflatable Moon, planets, and astronaut, Brune the Pirate videos and DJ music. This mix of science education and entertainment distinguishes Tribu's Festival from other traditional unreachable activities and even tourist activities, creating added value for audiences and local allies.
- Another additional element that was added to the Festival's ToC were the key assumptions, outlined at the bottom of the diagram (Figure 4). These assumptions clarify which aspects of the causal chain are external to Tribu but are crucial for achieving the intended impact. The evidence, especially interviews, showed that in order to happen the Festival requires the presence of favourable macro-political and economic con-

ditions to support the activities, including collaborative allocation of resources by public and private stakeholders, and local ownership and effective implementation of events to ensure they resonate with the community and are suitable in the long-term. The causal chain in the Festival's ToC is based on the hypothesis that improving scientific culture and social appropriation of science in small tourist towns in Jalisco depends on creating broader opportunities for children to engage in outreach and science education activities. In addition, it suggests that astro-tourism could be key to promoting sustainable involvement of local actors in the public, private and social sectors. The assumption analysis also helps to highlight potential risks to the successful outcomes of the festival in the transition from outputs to impacts. Some critical risks that this analysis reveals are policy changes, limited economic resources, or lack of local buy-in that would need to be addressed for the ToC to be met. Moreover, the festival's assumptions, beyond establishing the enabling conditions, highlight essential pillars for the success of the model.

- As a result of this research, one of the most significant adjustments to the Festival's ToC is the inclusion of a new strand of change related to what might be called *institutional change*, represented by the dotted arrow linking changes in children to changes in local governments and key actors. This element suggests that the development of astro-tourism in small, tourism-oriented towns in Jalisco can trigger not only individual-level changes in children—such as increased science awareness and skills—but also broader and systemic changes within the local context. This feedback loop, represented by the dotted arrow, illustrates how engaging children and the community in astronomy outreach can influence decision-makers to adopt more supportive policies and practices, thereby amplifying the impact of the festival. Although this hypothesis needs to be validated through impact evaluation, it suggests a promising pathway where changes in individual knowledge and attitudes can ripple outward to drive systemic changes in how science education and tourism are integrated at the local level. This focus on institutional change distinguishes the festival ToC

from the broader organizational ToC by highlighting the dual potential for personal and systemic impact through astro-tourism.

- In contrast to Tribu's organizational ToC, the final outcomes or impacts of the Festival's ToC are more specific for both children and local economic development. The ultimate impact envisioned includes improved science literacy, aspirations, and skills among children, emphasizing a direct educational benefit. In addition, the ToC integrates economic outcomes related to astro-tourism, with a focus on increased local economic revenue. This dual focus suggests that the festival's impact extends beyond education to support local economic development, making the ToC more comprehensive by linking scientific outreach to tangible economic benefits for the community. This approach contrasts with the organizational ToC, which has a broader and less specified focus on the social appropriation of science by providing a clearer and more measurable set of goals that address both the educational and economic dimensions of development.
- In contrast to the Organizational ToC, the Festival ToC was adapted to allow for a more detailed cause-effect analysis, while still aligning the Festival with the Tribu's overarching goal. While the organizational ToC presents a broad goal of increasing scientific literacy, the festival's ToC specifies its overarching goal as improving scientific culture and social appropriation of science specifically in small communities. This adaptation reflects a more targeted and actionable approach by directly linking science outreach to the local context and emphasizing its integration into both education and tourism strategies. By positioning astro-tourism as a mechanism for advancing these goals, the festival's ToC not only clarifies the pathway to impact but also ensures that the intended outcomes resonate with the immediate needs and priorities of the community. This makes the purpose more grounded in local realities and better aligned with sustainable development goals at the community level.

Limitations

While this exercise has provided Tribu with an actionable evaluation model for future

Astronomy Festivals, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, relying on data from self-reported participants and eyewitness testimony introduces a potential bias, as individuals may provide responses influenced by social desirability or subjective perceptions rather than objective reality. However, it is also worth noting that the researchers involved in collecting the data were locally based, which, given the qualitative nature of the study, allows for culturally appropriate interpretations of the data.

Another limitation of the study is that the applicability of the evaluation model in more diverse cultural settings remains untested. The ToC developed for the 2023-2024 Astronomy Festival design is context-specific, and any changes to the intervention in subsequent years will likely affect its current design.

By prioritising the local applicability of the ToC, we also sacrifice the generalisability of both the logic model and the findings of this evaluation to other contexts, limiting their broader utility. However, as we did with the literature review, this evaluation model can serve as an inspiration for other actors developing similar astro-tourism initiatives and inform the development of their own ToC and evaluation models, primarily benefitting from the methodology, methods and approaches rather than from the ToC model itself.

In addition, the final version of the ToC was not validated by the stakeholders who contributed to its development, raising concerns about its inclusivity and the extent to which it reflects the perspectives of all relevant parties. In addition, this study did not consider arts and cultural approaches to evaluation, which could provide alternative and more nuanced insights into the festival's impact. Finally, the costs and operational implications of implementing this ToC were not thoroughly assessed, potentially overlooking practical challenges that may arise during implementation.

These limitations suggest that future research should explore these dimensions in more depth, mainly by applying evaluation models to AFD projects in different sociocultural settings, validating them with stakeholders, and considering different evaluation approaches. In addition, a

comprehensive assessment of the ToC's financial and operational requirements will be critical to ensuring its sustainable implementation.

Discussion

This article presents a methodological and practical approach to developing evaluation models for civic-led AFD projects in developing countries, as demonstrated by the 3rd Astronomy Festival by Tribu. Integrating a backward design approach to developing a ToC and qualitative research to determine a plausible way to achieve the intended purpose provides an in-depth, culturally relevant and decision-oriented evaluation model for understanding the festival's immediate and long-term impacts.

This dual-focus approach ensures that the model is grounded in the local context's specific needs and realities and aligned with broader, more universal standards of impact assessment. This finding is consistent with the work of *Chapman et al. (2015)*, who stressed the importance of localised evaluation in grassroots initiatives.

The implications of this work for practice are significant. CSOs and community organisations can adopt this model to more comprehensively measure the success of their Astronomy for Development activities and use qualitative and participatory approaches to obtain feedback and learn to refine their AFD strategies. The model's flexibility is particularly noteworthy, as it can be adapted to different project goals and contexts, making it a valuable tool for various initiatives. This adaptability is crucial for CSOs, which often work in diverse and challenging environments where "high-level" or highly technical evaluation models may not be feasible.

This case also highlights several key lessons for advancing the field of AFD evaluation. First, while the existing literature around evaluation models is valuable for informing and accelerating local efforts, there is still much work to do in terms of designing evaluation methodologies that are practical and relevant for local actors. The contextual nuances of grassroots projects require a tailored approach to evaluation that considers local knowledge, needs, and capabilities, which is costly and sometimes

a "luxury" in the context of restricted funds or limited access to *pro bono* work from researchers and consultants.

In that sense, dedicated funding for mentoring and evaluation should be provided to strengthen the evidence base for AFD, particularly for citizen-led and CSO activities. This investment is critical to ensure these organisations can meaningfully contribute to the broader AFD evaluation agenda and share their learning with the global community.

Finally, evaluation must be seen as an iterative process requiring continuous reflection and improvement. In contexts where evaluation is often a luxury, the decision-focused approach (*Shah et al., 2015*) can help evaluation agendas flourish and foster a culture of continuous improvement and adaptation to local needs. This iterative mindset enhances the quality and relevance of evaluations and empowers local actors to take ownership of the process, leading to more sustainable and impactful results.

Conclusion

This article makes a novel contribution to astronomy for development evaluation by presenting a confirmed case of developing an evaluation model that fits community-specific needs while simultaneously creating conditions for locally driven evidence. The methodology and approaches to developing the 3rd Astronomy Festival evaluation model can inspire other actors implementing AFD projects in the Global South.

This research underscores the critical importance of involving stakeholders in the evaluation process to ensure that success measures are rigorous and contextually relevant. As CSOs continue to play a central role in community development, this framework provides a practical tool to guide their efforts and increase their impact, fostering more responsive and effective outreach initiatives.

Moving forward, it will be essential to engage stakeholders in validating the final version of the logic model, with particular attention to testing and refining its underlying assumptions to ensure that they accurately reflect the dynamics of the

intervention. This participatory approach will help solidify the relevance and applicability of the framework, especially as it is further refined for future editions of the Astronomy Festival in 2025. The selection and adaptation of specific indicators, tools and strategies will be critical to the effective implementation of the validated ToC, allowing the framework to evolve with the project.

Equally important is ensuring that the evaluation plan remains financially sustainable and operationally feasible. Careful consideration of resource allocation and planning will be necessary to maintain project momentum and impact over time.

Expanding collaborations represents a significant opportunity to advance evaluation efforts in AFD initiatives. While the partnership between ProSociedad and Tribu has already made significant progress, there is an urgent need for broader alliances to ensure that evaluations are comprehensive and impactful. Involving both public and private actors in implementing and evaluating AFD projects is a promising way to improve the quality and reach of these initiatives.

As we continue to refine and apply this framework, we encourage other organisations to join us in expanding the knowledge base on AFD in developing countries. By working together, we can contribute to more effective and meaningful community engagement, ultimately fostering stronger and more resilient communities through the power of astronomy.

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Biography

Ana Magdalena Rodríguez is the Co-founder and Co-director of ProSociedad, a development agency specialised in the design, evaluation and scaling up of evidence-based interventions for sustainable development. She has a master's in science (MSc) in Development Management from the London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE) and a Bachelor's degree in Industrial and Systems Engineering from the Tecnológico de Monterrey. She has worked with a wide range of development organisations, building capabilities with social, public and private sectors to improve the impact of development programs related to gender equality, education, early childhood development, economic inclusion and social protection programs.